

Profiles of selected collectors of Cayman Islands biodiversity

Wilmot W. Brown (1868–1953, American) collected birds and reptiles in all three Cayman Islands from April to July 1911. He also collected prolifically in Central and South America, contributing to the naming of numerous new species (Clark, 2020). On the Cayman Islands he collected many rare species including *Icterus leucopteryx* ssp. *bairdi* (Grand Cayman oriole) and *Turdus ravidus* (Grand Cayman thrush), both of which are now extinct. Brown was aware, even then, that they were close to extinction, but collected numerous specimens nevertheless, even though the Governor of the Islands forbade him (Clark, 2020). Most of his specimens are now at the Museum of Comparative Zoology Harvard (USA). Brown was a professional collector, living by his skill at hunting rare organisms, particularly birds, and selling their skins. He never published any scientific publications, even though his specimens contributed to numerous works.

Chapman Grant (1887–1983, American) collected in the Cayman Islands between April 1937 and August 1938 and subsequently wrote “The herpetology of the Cayman Islands”, published by Institute of Jamaica in which he described the endemic blue iguana *Cyclura lewisi* (Grant et al., 1940). He became a renowned and influential hepatologist in the USA, being publisher of the journal *Herpetologica* (Smith, 1986). It seems he always published alone.

William Randolph Taylor (1895–1990, American) collected marine algae on Grand Cayman for nine days in January 1967. He was a global authority on marine algae and collected tens of thousands of specimens from many countries, including many of the islands of the Caribbean. His collections are at the University of Michigan (Ann Arbor, USA), where he was on the faculty. He was also associated with the Marine Biological Laboratory at Woods Hole, Massachusetts (Davies, 1991; Hillis, 1992). He largely published alone, but Mr. Charles F. Rhyne of the Smithsonian Institution is credited as an author on the Marine Algae of Dominica (Taylor & Rhyne, 1970). The Institution was a sponsor of the survey. He also collaborated with Marshall Avery Howe (1867 – 1936) on the description of specimens from an earlier expedition to Brazil (Howe & Taylor, 1931).

George Richardson Proctor (1920 – 2015, American) visited the Cayman Islands 29 times between 1948 and 2004 (Proctor, 2012). Based on his, and other collections, he wrote the first edition of the Flora of the Cayman Islands, published in 1984, with a second revised edition being published in 2012. Proctor was one of the most important botanists of the Caribbean, contributing to Floras on Barbados (Gooding et al., 1965), Jamaica (Adams, 1972) and Puerto Rico and the Virgin Islands (Proctor, 1989). His specimens are in many collections, but particularly at the Institute of Jamaica and the Puerto Rico Department of Natural and Environmental Resources where he worked, and at the Natural History Museum, London.

Profiles of selected collectors of Montserrat biodiversity

Alexander Emanuel Agassiz (1835-1910, Swiss, and naturalised in the United States) joined the survey ship “Blake” on the 27th November 1878 and collected specimens on the 16th January 1879 off the coast of Montserrat, presumably as part of the dredge sampling conducted by the Blake (Agassiz et al., 1888). Agassiz was both a wealthy entrepreneur, marine biologist and scientific benefactor (Agassiz & Murray, 1910). His specimens are mainly at the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard University where he was curator at the time he collected these specimens. It is notable that it was his father, Louis Agassiz, who founded the Museum at Harvard and who preceded him as curator.

Richard Aiden Howard (1917-2003, American) visited Montserrat on at least five occasions, 1950, 1961, 1970, 1979 and 1980. On three of those occasions his wife, Elizabeth Solie Howard (1961, 1979, 1980), was a co-collector. Also, his sons Bruce (1970) and Philip (1979) are credited as co-collectors on separate trips. The longest period of collecting appears to be just 8 days. Howard was an influential botanist, being director of Harvard University’s Arnold Arboretum for 23 years (1954-1977) (Warnement & Wood, 2004). He collected widely in the Caribbean, publishing numerous papers about the plants of the region (Warnement et al., 2004). His research in the area ultimately led to the publication of the 6-volume *Flora of the Lesser Antilles* (1974-1989), which is still the primary reference for plants of the region. His specimens are held at many institutions, including Harvard University, The New York Botanical Garden and the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. However, it is notable that he left duplicate specimens in Montserrat and those specimens are now housed at the Montserrat National Trust herbarium.

Julius Oscar Boos (1946-2010, Trinidadian) collected reptiles on Montserrat over six days in August 1970. Boos was an amateur naturalist from Trinidad, but despite his amateur status he published fifteen papers on the taxonomy and identification of aroids, a beetle and a scorpion (Boos, 2010). Many of his specimens are held at The Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard University and at The University of the West Indies Zoology Museum in Trinidad.

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